

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

After three "fat" issues in the last four months this one is a slim one, yet with two very interesting papers. While the editorial team is breathing a sigh of relief that not all issues require the review and processing of dozens of papers, the next volume (a special issue on multimedia) is going to be another challenge!

The fact that J.UCS is publishing more and more special issues is indeed satisfactory, yet we also want to encourage as many individual contributions as possible. So, I want to invite not only all students of computer science to submit their papers to J.UCS, but also appeal to members of the J.UCS editorial board - since you are on the editorial board, why don't you either submit a paper yourself, or try to encourage your students or at least one bright colleague of yours to submit one good paper over the next year. If only 50% of you do this trivial job, J.UCS will be the largest journal in computer science!

Let us go for it! For now, happy reading!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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